

PACIFICUS

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“TEACHING WITH HEART, SERVING WITH LOVE”

The people in the community welcome you with open arms.

We create everything in service and love.

Futures are brightly illuminated and ignited by the beacon flame that is a teacher's heart.

I hold out my hand to people in need.

We stand as strong buddies and rise together.

Their visions come to life, their power is fully realized, lessons are gained and hope is given.

Each sentence is a commitment, a seed that has grown strong, and the chalkboard echoes the rhyme of wisdom.

I don't teach only to shape people's minds.

But to walk the correct way, to grow hearts.

My affection for the masses is growing.

The purpose varies in every life.

The call of a teacher, is always real, repeatedly making the world a better place.